

THE WEAR BEHAVIOR OF CONTINUOUS FIBER POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The wear behaviors of several composite materials consisting of unidirectional continuous fibers and polymer matrices were investigated. Specifically, the wear rates of the materials were examined under extreme tribological conditions; an abrasive wear condition and a sliding wear condition. The wear rates under the abrasive wear conditions were about five orders of magnitude higher than those under the sliding wear conditions. The composite materials exhibited anisotropic wear behaviors; however, for each material, the wear behaviors were different between the two tribological systems. Hence, wear is not an intrinsic material property, but depends on the tribological system under which it operates. An optimizing selection process yielded a low wear composite material whose constituents would include a PEEK matrix with aramid fibers oriented normal to the wear surface and carbon fibers oriented parallel to the wear surface.

INTRODUCTION

The term *tribology* contains the root word *tribo* which means "rubbing" in classic Greek. A literal translation of tribology refers to the study of rubbing. By definition, tribology is "the science and technology of interacting surfaces in relative motion ..." [1]. Many factors influence the wear behavior of materials as noted by Czichos [2] who described a systems approach towards tribology in detail. Basically, a tribological system can be

simplified into four main elements; two tribo-elements, the interfacial medium and the surrounding environment. In this study, the interfacial medium (no lubrication) and the environmental conditions will remain constant. One tribo-element is the composite specimen, and the other is the counterface material which will vary depending upon the system. Specifically, for the abrasive system, silica carbide paper was used as the counterface material; and for the sliding system, a smooth steel ring was used as the counterface material. Friedrich [3] has shown the effect of different counterface materials on the wear behavior of fiber reinforced polymers.

Wear is defined as the progressive loss of substance from the operating surface of a body occurring as a result of relative motion at the surface due to mechanical, chemical and thermal effects [1]. Sliding (adhesive) wear, the most common form of wear, is present in all mechanical systems in which two solids slide in contact with each other. It cannot be eliminated, only reduced. Abrasive wear, which can be the most detrimental to the wear life of a component, causes high material losses in short periods of time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two matrix materials in their neat form, epoxy (EP) and polyetheretherketone (PEEK or PK); and four composite systems, carbon/epoxy (CF-EP), glass/epoxy (GF-EP), aramid/epoxy (AF-EP) and carbon/PEEK (CF-PK), were examined in this wear behavior study. Table 1 describes these materials in more detail.

TABLE 1
Materials employed in the wear tests (V_f = fiber volume fraction).

Abbreviation	Material	V_f (%)	Density (g/cm^3)
EP	3501-6 epoxy resin	---	1.28
CF-EP	AS4 carbon fiber/epoxy	62	1.59
GF-EP	E-glass fiber/epoxy	58	2.01
AF-EP	K49 aramid fiber/epoxy	60	1.34
CF-PK	AS4 carbon fiber/PEEK	55	1.27
PK	polyetheretherketone(PEEK)	---	1.56

All feasible fiber orientations with respect to the sliding direction can be described by a two component descriptor (α, β). Figure 1 defines the α and β components with respect to the local fiber coordinate system (1-2-3). Rotations θ about the 2-axis are represented by α , and rotations about the 3-axis are represented by β . Hence, by definition, the rotations of the fibers about the 1-axis need not be recorded since they will not produce a different sliding

situation as far as fiber orientation is concerned. To facilitate for the achievement of all possible fiber orientations, the α -rotations must range from -90 to $+90$ degrees, and the β -rotations must range from 0 to 90 degrees.

Figure 2 illustrates the three basic fiber orientations which are commonly examined in the tribological study of unidirectional composite materials. When the fibers are perpendicular to the sliding surface plane the normal (N) orientation ($(\alpha, \beta) = (0, 0)$) exists. This orientation is further categorized as an out-of-plane orientation where the plane refers to the sliding surface plane. In the same context, the other two orientations are considered as in-plane orientations. More specifically, the parallel (P) orientation ($(\alpha, \beta) = (90, 0)$) exists when the fibers are in-plane and parallel to the sliding direction; and the antiparallel (AP) orientation ($(\alpha, \beta) = (0, 90)$) exists when the fibers are in-plane and perpendicular to the sliding direction.

Figure 1. The α and β components of the fiber orientation descriptor .

Figure 2. The basic fiber orientations for unidirectional composite materials.

Testing Procedures

The abrasive wear tests were performed on a pin-on-flat type apparatus, and the sliding wear tests were performed on a pin-on-ring type apparatus. A detailed description of these apparatuses are given in reference [3]. In each case, cubic specimens were tested whose

apparent contact area (A) was approximately 10 mm^2 . The counterface materials consisted of a 220 and 150 grit non-waterproof type silica carbide (SiC) abrasive paper for the abrasive wear tests. A detailed description of waterproof and non-waterproof type abrasive papers is given in reference [3]. According to the manufacturer, the average SiC particle diameter (D) was 70 and $15 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. A 100Cr6 (West German DIN specifications- 1% C,6% Cr) steel ring was used as the counterface material for the sliding wear tests. The average roughness of the ring at the beginning of the test was about $R_m=0.6 \mu\text{m}$.

For the abrasive wear tests, the specimens were slid against the SiC paper at a constant velocity (V) of 300 mm/min and at an apparent normal pressure (p) of 2.2 MPa for a sliding distance (L) of 500 mm . Four runs in the same direction were made for each specimen. Each run was on a fresh track of SiC paper (single-pass conditions). The mass loss of the specimen was observed after each run on a Mettler analytical balance (0.1 mg) under the same environmental conditions as the test was conducted. All tests were performed in controlled laboratory air which was at about 22°C and 35% relative humidity.

For the sliding wear tests, the specimens were slid against the steel ring which was 60 mm in diameter. The steel ring rotated at a constant velocity of 1.5 m/s and the appropriate load was applied such that the ($p \cdot V$) factor equaled 1.7 MPa m/s . The specimen always slid on the same track (multi-pass conditions). However, each specimen always started on a fresh track. All wear measurements were made in the steady-state regime.

The dimensionless wear rate (W) can be found by using the mass loss (Δm), the density of the specimen material (ρ), the sliding distance (L) and the apparent contact area of the specimen (A) in the following form:

$$W = \Delta m / \rho LA .$$

Dividing the dimensionless wear rate by the apparent normal pressure (p) yields the specific wear rate (W_s) as

$$W_s = W / p$$

which is given the dimensions of $\text{mm}^3/\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$. This describes the physical nature of the specific wear rate as a volume loss of material by a certain amount of energy input. Often, the wear resistance of a material is referred to which is simply the inverse of the wear rate (W^{-1} or W_s^{-1}).

Microscopic observations of the tested specimens were made by a scanning electron microscope (SEM). All surfaces which were microscopically observed under the scanning electron microscope were coated with a thin layer of gold following standard procedures for polymeric materials.

RESULTS

Abrasive Wear Rates

The averaged dimensionless wear rates of the materials under consideration in the three basic fiber orientations for the pin-on-flat wear tests are shown in Figure 3. Naturally, the wear rates for the more abrasive case (i.e., $D=70\ \mu\text{m}$) were greater than those of the less abrasive case. Similarly, the degree of anisotropic wear behavior was greater for the more abrasive case. Fiber reinforcement to the EP decreased its wear rate with the exception of the CF-EP and the GF-EP systems in the AP orientation only. Under both abrasive conditions, the wear rate of the PK was lower than that of the EP by a factor of about two. It is interesting to note that even though the two matrix materials show opposing trends in the effect of their wear rates due to carbon fiber reinforcement, both carbon fiber systems, CF-EP and CF-PK, exhibit the same magnitudes of wear rates.

In general, the N orientation generated the lowest wear rates, and the AP orientation generated the highest wear rates among each fiber/matrix system under the more abrasive conditions. The optimum wear resistances were shown by the AF-PK system when the fibers were in the N orientation.

Figure 3. Averaged dimensionless wear rates of the composite materials in the basic fiber orientations under abrasive wear conditions (pin-on-flat test).

Sliding Wear

The averaged specific wear rates of the materials under consideration in the three basic fiber orientations for the pin-on-ring wear tests are shown in Figure 4. Carbon and aramid fiber addition to the epoxy decreased the wear rate by approximately two orders of magnitude; whereas, glass fiber addition did not effect the wear rate as significantly. The wear rate of the PK material was about one order of magnitude lower than that of the EP material. Carbon fiber addition to the PK decreased the wear rate by about one order of magnitude for the in-plane fiber orientations. In general, the composite materials exhibited anisotropic wear behavior. Within each system, the P orientation generated the lowest wear rate with exception of the AF-EP material where the N orientation generated the lowest wear rate.

Figure 4. Averaged specific wear rates of the composite materials in the basic fiber orientations under sliding wear conditions (pin-on-ring tests).

Effect of Fiber Orientation on Wear Rate

The averaged dimensionless wear rate distribution of the CF-PK system for various fiber orientations are graphically illustrated in Figure 5(a). As the fibers proceeded from the P to AP and the N to AP orientations a relatively monotonic increase in the wear rate was observed. The wear rate distribution behaved in a non-symmetric fashion about the N orientation where a local maximum occurred at $(30,0)$ and $(-60,0)$. Furthermore, the absolute minimum occurred at the N orientation for the CF-PK system.

Wear rate is a function of material type as well as fiber orientation, as illustrated by the drastically different wear rate distribution of the AF-EP system shown in Figure 5(b). As the

fibers proceed from the P to AP orientation a relatively monotonic decrease in the wear rate was observed. Unlike the CF-PK system, the distribution of the wear rates behaved in a symmetric fashion about the N orientation. The absolute minimum occurred at the N orientation as well. Furthermore, the distribution was relatively flat about the N orientation illustrating the fact that the wear rate does not significantly increase as the fibers proceed from the out-of-plane orientations towards the in-plane orientations until they are predominantly in the in-plane orientation.

Figure 5. Dimensionless wear rate distributions for various fiber orientations (a) CF-PK and (b) AF-EP. Abrasive wear conditions $p=2.2$ MPa, $V=300$ mm/min and $D=70$ μm SiC paper.

DISCUSSION

Wear Rates Among Different Systems

The wear behavior of the composite materials was characterized by measuring their wear rates under specified tribological systems. A network of wear data was created for the materials with respect to three material parameters; fiber orientation, fiber material and matrix material. A general point of view can be taken towards the wear behavior of the composite materials in such a way as to establish the relative effectiveness of fiber reinforcement to the neat matrices in different tribological systems. The initial roughness of the steel ring used in the pin-on-ring sliding wear tests was measured to be about $R_m=0.6$ μm . For the sake of generality, R_m will be assumed to be equivalent to D ; therefore, a comparison can be made of the wear rates among the different wear systems. Table 2 tabulates the relative wear resistances (ratio of the wear resistance of the composite material to the wear resistance of the epoxy material) of the composite materials as a function of the material parameters for the more abrasive tribological system and the sliding type tribological system, respectively. This

table shows that the wear resistance is improved up to about 8 times in the more abrasive wear case, whereas, the improvement is up to about 160 times in the sliding wear case.

TABLE 2
Wear resistance ratios

reinf matrix		CF	GF	AF	neat
		EP	N 1.8 P 1.7 AP 0.9	2.3 1.4 0.8	7.9 1.1 1.2
PK	N	1.7			1.8
	P	1.6			
	AP	1.0			

reinf matrix		CF	GF	AF	neat
		EP	N 65.4 P 99.8 AP 44.1	0.5 2.1 1.1	122 44.1 46.3
PK	N	4.9			11.8
	P	158			
	AP	94.8			

Ideally, a systematic selection of the optimum variation of each parameter can be done in order to develop a low wear composite material. In both these cases, the low wear model material would consist of a Peek matrix incorporating aramid fibers oriented normal to the contacting surface and carbon fibers oriented parallel to the contacting surface. This is schematically illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6. Ideal low wear composite material.

CONCLUSIONS

The wear behavior of selected epoxy and PEEK matrix composite materials have been investigated in terms of wear rates under an abrasive wear condition and a sliding wear

condition. Like many properties inherent to composite materials, the wear behavior was also shown to possess anisotropic characteristics. However, the wear behavior is not an intrinsic material property, but it depends on the tribological system in which it functions. This was shown by the varying degrees of anisotropic wear behavior of the composite materials under each different wear condition. A slight improvement of the wear resistance of the neat matrix materials was shown in the abrasive case, however, a much greater improvement was displayed in the sliding wear case. A tabulation of all the data resulted in a network of data on the wear behavior of the selected composite materials with respect to three material parameters; fiber orientation, fiber material and matrix material. By normalizing the data with respect to the wear rate of the epoxy, a systematic selection of the necessary material parameters were selected for an ideal low wear composite material. This material would consist of a PEEK matrix with aramid fibers oriented normal to the wear surface and carbon fibers oriented parallel to the wear surface.

A fundamental approach was taken towards the selected composite materials in order to characterize their wear behaviors. This resulted in some basic information which should serve as a data base to aide the understanding and evaluation of more complicated materials operating in various tribological systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was sponsored by the Center for Composite Materials at the University of Delaware and the Polymer and Composites Group at the Technical University of Hamburg-Harburg in West Germany. Also, part of the work on the PEEK materials at Hamburg was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, FRI-675-1-1).

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